

The Buddhist community on Mount Lu during early medieval China

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Buddhist Traditions, Chinese Buddhist Traditions, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region, Chinese Buddhism

Mount Lu (Lu Shan 廬山), located in present-day Jiangxi province of China, rose to become an important center of Buddhist scholarship and practice in early medieval China under the leadership of the scholar-monk Huiyuan 慧遠 (334 CE–416 CE). Huiyuan came to Mount Lu with his disciples, associates, and his brother Huichi 慧持 (337–412) in 381 CE following the disintegration of the monastic community of Xiangyang 襄陽 during the war between the Former Qin (Qian Qin 前秦; 351–394) and the Eastern Jin (Dong Jin 東晉; 317–420). With the help of his former colleague Huiyong 慧永 (332–414), who had settled on the mountain a few years earlier, and the financial support from the local governor Huan Yi 桓伊 (d.u.; Governor of Jiangzhou 江州 since 384), Huiyuan's community soon grew into one of the most important centers of Buddhism in South China. The community drew such influential Buddhist scholar-monks of the time as Huiguan 慧觀 (d.u.), Huirui 慧叡 (d.u.), and Daosheng 道生 (355–434), as well as such lay intellectuals of renown as Zhou Xuzhi 周續之 (d. 423), Liu Yimin 劉遺民 (354–410), Lei Cizong 雷次宗 (386–448), and Zong Bing 宗炳 (375–443). Mount Lu also was the site of a few important translation workshops during this time. In the early 390s, Saṅghadeva (fl. 383–397) translated two important Abhidharma texts, the *_Apitan xin lun_ 阿毘曇心論* (T 1550) and the *_San fadu lun_ 三法度論* (T 1506), and in the early 410s, Buddhahadra (359–429) translated the meditation text *_Damoduoluo chan jing_ 達摩多羅禪經* (T 618). In this animated intellectual environment, Huiyuan authored such representative Buddhist treatises of the time as the *_Shamen bujing wangzhe lun_ 沙門不敬王者論* and the *_Ming baoying lun_ 明報應論*, where he articulated his theory of the imperishability of the soul (*_shen bumie_ 神不滅*) that was to exert lasting influence on Chinese Buddhists' understanding of the mind. In terms of Buddhist practice, the Buddhist community of Mount Lu is where some of the earliest examples of the cult of Amitabha and the belief in the rebirth in Amitabha's Western Pure Land are associated with. For example, in 402, the 123 members community took a collective vow to be reborn in the Western Pure Land before a statue of Amitabha Buddha. Another important example of Buddhist art created by this group was the Buddha-image (Foying 佛影) Grotto. The renowned grotto was constructed in 413 relying on the oral reports about the Buddha-image cave of the Indian city of Nagarhāra and enshrined a painting of the Buddha, whose excellence in turn inspired its own copies to be made and circulated. In this way, the Buddhist community of Mount Lu during early medieval China developed a rich and lively religious culture involving scholarship, devotionism, and art and architecture.

Date Range: 350 CE - 450 CE

Region: Mount Lu

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China, South Central China

Mount Lu (Lu shan), one of the main centers of Buddhism and Daoism in China

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Zürcher, Erik. 1959. "The Centres at Hsian-yang, Chiang-ling and Lu-shan, and the Influence of Northern Buddhism." Chap. 4 in *The Buddhist Conquest of China: The Spread and Adaptation of Buddhism in Early Medieval China*. Leiden: E.J. Brill.
- Source 2: Tsukamoto Zenryū. 1985. "Hui-yüan and His Circle." Chap. 8 in *A History of Early Chinese Buddhism: From Its Introduction to the Death of Hui-yüan*. Translated by Leon Hurvitz. New York: Kodansha International.
- Source 3: Lee, Sangyop. 2019. "Lushan Huiyuan." In *Brill's Encyclopedia of Buddhism*, vol. 2, edited by Jonathan A. Silk, Vincent Eltschinger, Richard Bowring, and Michael Radich, 711-21. Leiden: Brill.
- Source 1: Kimura Eiichi 木村英一, ed. 1960. *Eon kenkyū: Ibun hen* 慧遠研究: 遺文篇. Tokyo: Sōbunsha.
- Source 2: Li Xingling 李幸玲. 2007. *Lushan Huiyuan yanjiu* 廬山慧遠研究. Taipei: Wanjuanlou, 2007.
- Source 3: Li Qinhe 李勤合. 2016. *Lushan Huiyuan jiaotuan yanjiu* 廬山慧遠教團研究. Beijing: Shehui kexue wenxian chubanshe.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://referenceworks.brillonline.com/entries/encyclopedia-of-buddhism/lushan-huiyuan-COM_2101?lang=de
- Source 1 Description: Brill's Encyclopedia Entry on Lushan Huiyuan (廬山慧遠; 334–416), who led the Mount Lu Buddhist community in the late 4th and the early 5th century.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: https://cbetaonline.dila.edu.tw/zh/T2059_001
- Source 1 Description: *Gaoseng zhuan* 高僧傳, a collection of monastic biographies compiled by Huijiao 慧皎 (497–554) in the early sixth century, in which biographies of many central members of the Mount Lu community can be found.
- Source 2 URL: https://cbetaonline.dila.edu.tw/zh/T2145_001
- Source 2 Description: *Chu sanzang ji ji* 出三藏記集, a collection of bibliographical sources related to the translation of Buddhist texts (chronological catalogue, prefaces and colophons, biographies of translators, etc.) compiled by Sengyou 僧祐 (445–518) in the early sixth century, in which texts written by the members of Mount Lu community survive.
- Source 3 URL: https://cbetaonline.dila.edu.tw/zh/T2102_001
- Source 3 Description: *Hong ming ji* 弘明集, a collection of apologetical and propagandistic texts compiled by Sengyou 僧祐 (445–518) in the early sixth century, in which texts written by the members of the Mount Lu community survive.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Y a-t-il d'autres groupes religieux en contact culturel avec la religion cible:

- Yes

Notes: Mount Lu was also an important center of Daoism in early medieval China. However, no record survives of the interactions between Huiyuan's community and Daoist practitioners of the region.

Reference: Wu 吳, Guofu 國富. *Lu Shan Daojiao Shi 廬山道教史*. Nanchang: Jiangxi renmin chubanshe, 2011.

↳ Est-ce que le contact culturel est compétitif (à l'intérieur de la région échantillon):
– Yes

↳ Est-ce que le contact culturel est accommodant/pluriel:
– Yes

↳ Est-ce que le contact culturel est neutre:
– Yes

↳ Y a-t-il un conflit violent (à l'intérieur de la région échantillon):
– No

↳ Y a-t-il un conflit violent (avec les groupes à l'extérieur de la région échantillon):
– No

Est-ce que le group religieux possède un processus ou un système pour déterminer l'appartenance religieuse:

– Yes

Notes: Although no record about such a process for this particular group survives, we can infer that they would have followed the ritual norms of contemporary Chinese Buddhists, where taking up a certain set of precepts signified becoming a lay or a monastic member of the Buddhist community.

↳ Déterminée par la naissance (l'appartenance est par défaut au sein de cette société):
– No

↳ Déterminée par un choix personnel:
– Yes

↳ Déterminée par la classe sociale:
– No

↳ Attribuée à un âge spécifique:
– No

↳ Déterminée par le genre:

– Yes

↳ Déterminée par la participation à un rituel particulier:

– Yes

↳ Déterminée par tout autre facteur (spécifiez):

– No

Est-ce que le groupe fait activement du prosélytisme et recrute de nouveaux membres:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are records of its members inviting other Buddhists to join them (e.g. T 2059.50:329a8-13), but there is not enough evidence to tell if recruitment of new members was a distinguishing and meaningful characteristic of this community.

Est-ce que le groupe religieux reçoit du support politique officiel:

– Yes

Notes: The Mount Lu community is known to have received favorable treatments from the central figures of the Eastern Jin court. Also, like many other Buddhist communities of medieval times, they depended on the donation and support from the members of the political elite. The central monastery of this community, Eastern Grove Monastery (Donglin si 東林寺), for example, was established by the Inspector of Jiangzhou Huan Yi 桓伊 (?-391) ca. 386 (T 2059.50:358a29-b3; T 2095.51:1039b2-3). Also, a translation workshop was carried out with the support from the Inspector of Jiangzhou Wang Ningzhi 王凝之 (334-399; successor of Huan Yi) and the Governor of Xiyang Ren Guzhi 任固之 (d.u.) between the years 391 and 392 (T 2145.55:72b21-28). It should also be noted that Xunyang 尋陽 (corresponding roughly to present-day Jiujiang city 九江市), the provincial capital of Jiangzhou, was right next to Mount Lu, which would have facilitated the interaction and collaboration between the Buddhist community and the political elite. However, for this time period, it is difficult to decide whether such support implied official ties with the government or was merely seen as private matters of the persons who happen to hold government offices.

Reference: Zürcher, Erik. *The Buddhist Conquest of China*. BRILL, 2007.

https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Buddhist_Conquest_of_China.html?hl=&id=GYSKhU7UW-cC. p.211-17.

↳ Est-ce que les prêtres sont payés par le régime politique:

– No

Notes: Although they were not directly paid by the polity, the Buddhist clergy would have relied largely on the donation from the members of the political elite.

↳ Est-ce que le régime politique paie pour les infrastructures religieuses:

– No

Notes: Although they were not directly paid by the polity, Buddhist construction projects would

have relied largely on the donation from the members of the political elite.

↳ Est-ce que la personne qui est à la tête du régime politique est la même que la personne qui est à la tête du groupe religieux:

– No

↳ Est-ce que les responsables politiques sont les mêmes que les responsables religieux:

– No

↳ Est-ce que la pratique religieuse est imposée par le régime politique:

– No

Notes: However, there was an attempt by the central government in 402 to single out and expel monks who were not capable of upholding the precepts and observing seclusion from secular society. The head of the Mount Lu community, Huiyuan 慧遠 (334–416), famously argued for relaxing the standards for excommunication of monks in an epistolary correspondence with Huan Xuan 桓玄 (369–404; this correspondence survives in T 2102.52:85a12–c5) and also succeeded in exempting the Mount Lu community from the investigation.

Reference: Zürcher, Erik. *The Buddhist Conquest of China*. BRILL, 2007.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Buddhist_Conquest_of_China.html?hl=&id=CYsKhU7UW-cC. p.236–37.

↳ Le code juridique du régime politique coïncide presque parfaitement avec le code religieux:

– No

↳ Le régime politique offre des privilèges économiques (par exemple: exemptions fiscales):

– Yes

Notes: The members of the Buddhist monastic community were exempted from tax and corvée labor duties in medieval China.

Y a-t-il une conception de l'apostasie dans la religion:

– No

Size and Structure

Nombre de membres dans le groupe religieux à l'intérieur de la région échantillon (population estimée, en valeur numérique)

– Estimated population, numeric: 123

Notes: The exact number of this community must have changed constantly over time. However, one record written by Liu Yimin 劉遺民 (a central lay member of the community; 354–410) in the year 402

mentions 123 lay and monastic participants being present at a votive ritual carried out at the "Prajñā Terrace" on the mountain (T 2059.50:358c24–26). Yet another record produced by this community around the year 391 reports that 80 monastics participated at a translation workshop carried out on the mountain (T 2145.55:72b25–28; according to some records, this workshop also took place at the "Prajñā Terrace"; T 2145.55: 99c17–20; T 2059.50:329 a10–13). Finally, the biography of the monk Huiyong 慧永 reports that the entourage of Huiyuan, the leader of the Mount Lu community, consisted of "one hundred monks" (T 2059.50:362a28–b1).

Nombre de membres dans le groupe religieux à l'intérieur de la région échantillon (% de la région échantillon, en valeur numérique)

– Field doesn't know

Nature du groupe [Veuillez, s'il-vous-plaît, choisir un choix parmi les suivants]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Y a-t-il des leaders reconnus au sein du groupe religieux:

– Yes

Notes: Huiyuan (334–416) is known to have represented the Buddhist community on Mount Lu while he resided at Eastern Grove Monastery (Donglin si) from 386 to 416. However, this was more likely due to his personal charisma rather than there being an institutionally recognized position of the head of the Mount Lu community. This can be inferred from the fact that after Huiyuan's death, no single monk of the community seems to have taken over the representative role he used to assume.

Y a-t-il une hiérarchie parmi ces leaders:

– Field doesn't know

Croit-on que les leaders possèdent des qualités ou pouvoirs surnaturels:

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of miracles stories attributed to the leader of this community, Huiyuan (334–416). Refer to his biographies in the *_Chu sanzang ji ji_* and the *_Gaoseng zhuan_*.

Les pouvoirs sont acquis par le biais d'actions individuelles réalisées au cours de vies précédentes:

– Yes

Notes: Although the miracles stories associated with Huiyuan do not offer an explicit explanation of the provenance of his supernatural powers, it is likely that people at the time believed them to have resulted from his engagement in Buddhist practices, either in his current life or during his previous lives.

Les pouvoirs sont acquis par le biais d'actions individuelles réalisées au cours de la vie présente:

– Yes

↳ Les pouvoirs sont hérités:

– No

↳ Les pouvoirs sont transmis culturellement par le biais d'un être surnaturel:

– No

↳ Les pouvoirs sont transmis culturellement par le biais d'un autre être humain (par exemple: précepteur):

– No

↳ Les pouvoirs des leaders dérivent du poste de leadership qu'ils prennent en charge:

– No

↳ Les leaders religieux sont choisis:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Est-ce que les leaders sont considérés comme étant faillibles:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Est-ce que les disciples d'un leader religieux sont tenus d'accepter docilement et sans conteste les déclarations du leader en toutes matières:

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Est-ce que le groupe religieux possède des écritures:

"Écritures" est un terme générique qui désigne des textes vénérés qui sont particulièrement considérés sacrés et comme contenant une autorité par rapport à d'autres textes. À proprement parler, ce terme fait référence à des textes écrits mais il existe également des "écritures orales" (par exemple: Les Védas en Inde)

– Yes

Notes: There is no reason to believe that the group had a distinctive notion of their own religious canon. It is more likely that they would have followed the received notion of the Buddhist canon among contemporary Chinese Buddhists. The group did contribute to the formation of the Chinese Buddhist canon by producing a number of new translations (_Apitan xin lun_ 阿毘曇心論 [T no. 1550]; _San fadu lun_ 三法度論 [T no. 1506]; _Damoduoluo chan jing_ 達摩多羅禪經 [T no. 618]) by collaborating with Indian monks such as Saṅghadeva (fl. 383-397) and Buddhabhadra (359-429), who resided on Mount

Lu respectively during the 390s and around 410. The circumstances of the translations of these texts can be found in the records written by the participants at the workshops (preserved in the *_Chu sanzang ji ji_*; T. 2145.55:65b22-66a23; 72b16-28; 72b29-73a1; 73a2-29).

↳ Sont-elles écrites:

– Yes

↳ Sont-elles orales:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Sont-elles révélées par un dieu supérieur:

– No

↳ Sont-elles révélées par tout autre être surnaturel:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider the Buddha as a supernatural being, then the Buddhist belief would be that the Buddhist sūtras are indeed revealed by a supernatural being.

↳ Sont-elles inspirées par un dieu supérieur:

– No

↳ Sont-elles inspirées par tout autre être surnaturel:

– No

↳ Prennent-elles origine dans des êtres divins ou semi-divins:

– Yes

Notes: If we define the Buddha as a semi-divine human being, then the Buddhist belief would be that Buddhist sūtras indeed have originated from a semi-divine human being.

↳ Prennent-elles origine dans des êtres humains non-divins:

– Yes

Notes: If we consider the Buddha as a non-divine human being, then the Buddhist belief would be that the Buddhist sūtras are indeed revealed by a non-divine human being.

↳ Les écritures sont-elles modifiables:

– Yes

Notes: If we see translation as a kind of alteration, Buddhist scriptures are indeed alterable.

↳ Existe-t-il des institutions formelles (c'est-à-dire des institutions qui sont autorisées par la communauté religieuse ou par les leaders politiques) pour interpréter les écritures:

– No

↳ Existe-t-il un groupe privilégié de personnes formées pour la transmission des écritures:

– No

↳ Existe-t-il un canon codifié d'écritures:

– No

Notes: However, there were multiple attempts at creating a comprehensive catalogue of available Buddhist texts around this time, notably now-lost *_Zongli zhongjing mulu_* 綜理衆經目錄 by Dao'an 道安 (312/314–385), which is reproduced in the *_Chu sanzang ji ji_* 出三藏記集.

Architecture, Geography

L'architecture monumentale religieuse est-elle présente:

– Yes

Notes: Mount Lu during this period was home to a number of important Buddhist establishments. 1) Eastern Grove Monastery (Donglin si 東林寺) was donated to Huiyuan by the Inspector of Jiangzhou Huan Yi 桓伊 (?–391) (T 2059.50:358a29–b3; T 2095.51:1039b2–3). Its construction began in 384 and was completed in 386. Huiyuan resided here until his death in 416. 2) Western Grove Monastery (Xilin si 西林寺) was donated to Huiyong 慧永 by Tao Fan 陶範 (d.u., but likely one of the sons of the Eastern Jin general Tao Kan 陶侃 [259–334]; he had ties with this region and Fan 範 is listed among the names of his sons in the *_Jin shu_* 晉書 fasc. 66; T 2059.50:362a14–15). According to later records, Tao Fan was the Inspector of Jiangzhou (T 2035.49:265b21–23; T 2095.51:1040b18–20). If these records are reliable, he must have occupied this office before Huan Yi (who assumed the same office in 384). A stele erected in 617 specifies the year of the establishment of this monastery to 367 (T 2095.51:1029b2–10). 3) Prajñā Platform (Bore tai 般若臺; alternatively, 波若臺 Bore tai): This was the place where the members of the community gathered in 402 to make the vow to be reborn together in the Western Pure Land (the votive text recited at this occasion is preserved in T 55.2145:109c12–110a9). Also, according to some records, this was where Saṃghadeva translated the *_Apitan xin lun_* 阿毘曇心論 (T no. 1550) and the *_San fadu lun_* 三法度論 (T no. 1506) around 391 (T 2059.50:329a10–13; T 2145.55:99c17–20). This structure was under construction when Baoyun 寶雲 visited Mount Lu in 389 (X 1523.77:358c7–9). 4) Buddha-image (Foying 佛影) Grotto, also known later as the Buddha-image Platform (Foying tai 佛影臺): Inspired by oral reports about the Buddha-image cave in the Indian city of Nagarahāra, and relying on the details described by Buddhahadra when he was visiting the mountain around 410 (Chen 2011), Huiyuan led the construction of this grotto in 412 (T 2103.52:198b5–8), wherein a painting that depicted the Buddha-image in the Nagarahāra cave was enshrined. Huiyuan's also wrote a eulogy (ming 銘) of the Buddha-image, which survives together with its preface and postscript (T 2103.52:197c7–198b13; cf. T 2059.50:358b14–c3). Among these establishments, Eastern Grove Monastery and Western Grove

Monastery still remain, although none of the current architectural structures dates back to this period. Also, although stūpas were not uncommon in contemporary Buddhist monasteries in China, no record about a stūpa in this community survives.

Reference: Chen, Jinhua. "Buddhabhadra's (359–429) Collaboration with Huiyuan (334–416) in Transplanting the Nagarahāra Image-cave to China: A Reexamination". In *Chūgoku Indo Shūkyōshi, Tokuni Bukkyō Shi Ni Okeru Shomotsu No Ryūtsū Denpa to Jinbutsu Idō No Chiiki Tokusei* 中国印度宗教史とくに仏教史における書物の流通伝播と人物移動の地域特性, edited by Tōru 徹 Funayama 船山. Kyoto: Kyōto Daigaku Jinbun Kagaku Kenkyūjo, 2011.

↳ Dans un établissement moyen, quel est le pourcentage d'espace occupé par tous les monuments religieux:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Taille du plus grand monument religieux, en mètres carrés:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Hauteur du plus grand monument religieux, en mètres:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Taille d'un monument moyen, en mètres carrés:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Hauteur d'un monument moyen, en mètres:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Dans l'établissement le plus grand, quel est le pourcentage d'espace occupé par tous les monuments religieux:

– Field doesn't know

Existe-t-il différents types d'architecture monumentale religieuse:

– Yes

↳ Tombes:

– Yes

Notes: There is only one mention about burial practices in the records related to this group: When Huiyuan died, his disciples first exposed his body in the wild and later collected his remains and buried at the western ridge of Mount Lu. A stele and a structure to house the stele were also established. (T 2059.50:361b6-10.)

↳ Cimetières:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: See the above discussion of Eastern Grove Monastery and Western Grove Monastery. Although they were principally monasteries, many of them would have functioned also as places for making offerings to Buddhist deities.

↳ Autels:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although there is no specific mention about an alter, it is likely that the monasteries of this community as well as places like the Prajñā Platform and the Buddha-image Grotto would have had alter-like structures.

↳ Marqueurs dévotionnels:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Points de rassemblement de masse [places publiques, cour, carré. Endroits démarqués de façon permanente par des objets ou structures]:

– Yes

Notes: See the discussion above. The Prajñā Platform seems to have been often used for large communal gatherings.

↳ Autre [précisez]:

– Yes [specify]: See the discussion above.

L'iconographie est-elle présente:

– Yes

↳ Où est-ce que l'iconographie est-elle présente [veuillez sélectionner tous les choix qui s'appliquent]:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Other than the records related to the Buddha-image Grotto, we do not have records describing the group's iconographic practices.

↳ L'iconographie du groupe religieux possède-t-elle des caractéristiques distinctes:

– Yes

Notes: The anecdote that copies of the painting of the Buddha-image enshrined in the

Buddha-image Grotto were transmitted as far as the southern capital (T. 2145.55:109c6-11) suggests that their iconography had distinctive and appealing features.

- ↳ Yeux (stylisés ou non):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Êtres surnaturels (zoomorphes)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Êtres surnaturels (géomorphiques)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Êtres surnaturels (anthropomorphiques)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Êtres surnaturels (symbole abstrait)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Dépictions de la vie après la mort:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Aspects de la doctrine (par exemple: croix, Trinité, symboles)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Êtres humains:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Autre [précisez]:
 - Yes

Existe-t-il des sites spécifiquement dédiés aux pratiques sacrées ou considérées comme sacrées:

– Yes

- ↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:
"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Les pèlerinages sont-ils présents:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

La distinction corps-esprit est-elle présente:

Répondez "non" seulement si la qualité de personne (ou conscience) s'éteint avec la mort du corps physique. Répondre "oui" ne signifie pas nécessairement qu'il existe une dualité cartésienne corps/esprit mais que certains éléments de la qualité de personne (ou conscience) demeurent après la mort du corps.

– Yes

Notes: Huiyuan was one of the leading theorists of the doctrine of the imperishability of the soul (shen bumie 神不滅), authoring a number of important treatises on this topic such as the *_Elucidation of Retribution_* (Ming baoying lun 明報應論; T 2102. 52:33b9–34b2) and *_A Monk Does Not Revere the King_* (Shamen bujing wangzhe lun 沙門不敬王者論; T 2102.52:29c19–32b11). His lay disciple Zong Bing authored the *_Elucidation of Buddhism_* (Ming fo lun 明佛論; T 2102.52:9b5–16a24), which also contains a rich discussion of the idea of the imperishable soul. For recent attempts to understand this doctrinal deviation, see Park 2012 and Radich 2017. While Park sees it as a result of mistranslation and misunderstanding of Indian Buddhism, Radich sees it as a theoretical continuation of Indian Buddhist notions of consciousness.

Reference: Park, Jungnok. *How Buddhism Acquired a Soul on the Way to China*. Equinox, n.d..

↳ L'esprit est conçu comme ayant qualitativement des propriétés ou des pouvoirs différents que les autres parties du corps:

– Yes

Notes: Huiyuan claimed that our sentience (i.e. the ability to perceive objects through the sense organs) was the result of the soul's entrapment in the body. Thus according to Huiyuan, the body on its own would lack the ability to sense or perceive objects, like other material elements of the world. See T 2012:34a3–5.

↳ L'esprit est conçu comme étant non-matériel et ontologiquement différent du corps:

– Yes

Notes: Arguing against the mainstream Daoist metaphysics of his time, Huiyuan claimed that while the body is made of the physical energy (qi 氣), the soul was not reducible into a form of this physical energy and thus was imperishable. See T 2102.52:31b11–c14. The same understanding of the soul can be found in his disciple Zong Bing's thought. See T 2102.52:9c26–10a4, 10a15–18, 10a28b–2, 13a24–26.

↳ Autre [précisez]:

– Yes [specify]: Huiyuan had a distinctively negative view about the body.

Notes: Huiyuan describes the bodily life as the "fetters and manacles" that bind the soul in the material world, and he claims that Buddhist nirvana is achieved by freeing the soul from the fetters of the bodily life. See T 2102.52:30c10-17. Zong Bing similarly thought that bodily desires were responsible for the sentient being's degeneration and that the Buddhist ideal was achieved by realizing an immaterial state of being in which the soul existed without a body. See T 2102.52:10b10-12, c7-10. This belief of the group was used to provide a theoretical justification of the self-immolation practice of the time. See T 2102.52:14a20-22 for Zong Bing's justification of the practice, and T 2059.50:405a10-11 for an example of this practice by one of the monks of the Mount Lu community, Sengyu 僧瑜 (d.u.).

Croyance en la vie après la mort:

– Yes

Notes: This group is associated with some of the earliest examples of the cult of Amitabha Buddha in China. According to this cult, one can achieve a rebirth in the Buddha-realm of Amitabha in the west (commonly referred to as the Western Pure Land) simply by taking refuge in Amitabha Buddha. For examples of the group's practice of this cult, see the following sources: 1) A votive text written in 402 by Huiyuan's lay disciple Liu Yimin 劉遺民 (354-410) for the occasion of a collective vow by the 123 lay and monastic members of the group to be reborn in the Western Pure Land together. (T 2059.50:358c23-359a20; an English translation is given in Zürcher 1959, 244-45). 2) The death-bed story of Huiyuan's monastic colleague Huiyong 慧永 (d. 414), where he reports seeing Amitabha Buddha just before passing away. (T. 2059.50:362b5-10.) 3) The death-bed story of Huiyuan's disciple Sengji 僧濟 (d.u.), where he sees Amitabha Buddha in a dream at the night of his death. (T. 2059.50:362b16-27.) See Zürcher (1959, 219-23) and Jones (2008, 187-88) for further discussions of these sources.

Reference: Zürcher, Erik. *The Buddhist Conquest of China*. BRILL, 2007.

https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Buddhist_Conquest_of_China.html?hl=&id=GYsKhU7UW-cC.

Reference: Jones, Charles B.. "Was Lushan Huiyuan a Pure Land Buddhist? Evidence from His Correspondence with Kumārajīva About Nianfo Practice". *Zhonghua Foxue Xuebao* 21 (January 1, 2008).

↳ Est-ce que la localisation spatiale de la vie après la mort est spécifiée ou décrite par le groupe:

– Yes

↳ La vie après la mort se trouve dans un domaine de l'espace au-delà de ce monde:

– Yes

↳ La vie après la mort se trouve dans un "au-delà" de l'espace vaguement défini:

– Yes

Notes: In the mainstream Buddhist cosmology, the realms of deities and semi-deities are believed to exist above the realm of humans.

↳ La vie après la mort se trouve dans un "en-deça" de l'espace vaguement défini:

– Yes

Notes: In the mainstream Buddhist cosmology, the various hells are believed to be located below the realm of humans.

↳ La vie après la mort se trouve dans un espace horizontal vaguement défini:

– Yes

Notes: The Western Pure Land is believed to exist in the west.

↳ Autre [précisez]:

– Yes [specify]: According to the mainstream Buddhist cosmology there are numerous cosmoses.

Réincarnation dans ce monde:

– Yes

↳ Dans une forme humaine:

– Yes

↳ Dans une forme animale ou végétale:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhists in general believe that sentient beings can be reborn as animals, but not plants.

↳ Dans la forme d'un ou des objets inanimés:

– No

↳ Dans une forme non individuelle (c'est-à-dire sous forme, par exemple, de renaissance collective, de tribu ou de lignée familiale, etc.):

– No

↳ Réincarnation liée à une notion de causalité transcendante (par exemple: karma):

– Yes

↳ Autre [précisez]:

– Yes [specify]: Other than animals and humans, it is believed that sentient beings can be reborn as semi-gods, gods, hungry ghosts, and the denizens of hells.

Y a-t-il des traitements spéciaux pour le corps des membres du groupe religieux:

– Yes

Notes: There is only one mention about burial practices in the records related to this group: When Huiyuan died, his disciples first exposed his body in the wild and later collected his remains and buried at the western ridge of Mount Lu. A stele and a structure to house the stele were also established. See T 2059.50:361b6-10.

Crémation:

– Field doesn't know

Momification:

– Field doesn't know

Inhumation:

– Yes

Cannibalisme:

– Field doesn't know

Exposition à des éléments (par exemple: séché à l'air):

– Yes

Donné à manger aux animaux:

– Yes

Inhumation secondaire:

– Field doesn't know

Traitement secondaire du corps:

– Yes

Autre traitement intensif (en terme de temps et ressources dépensés) du corps [précisez]:

– Field doesn't know

Y a-t-il présence de co-sacrifices lors d'inhumations dans des tombes ou lors d'enterrements:

– Field doesn't know

Les biens funéraires sont-ils présents:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les enterrements formels sont présents:

– Yes

Notes: There is only one mention about burial practices in the records related to this group: When Huiyuan died, his disciples first exposed his body in the wild and later collected his remains and buried at the western ridge of Mount Lu. A stele and a structure to house the stele were also established. See T 2059.50:361b6-10.

↳ Comme cénotaphe:

– Yes

Notes: See the note above.

↳ Dans un cimetière:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Tombe-crypte familiale:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Domestique (les individus sont enterrés sous la maison ou dans des endroits utilisés pour la conduite d'activités domestiques normales):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Autre [précisez]:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Est-ce que les êtres surnaturels sont présents:

– Yes

↳ Un dieu supérieur suprême est présent:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In the surviving writings of the group, we find no evidence of a belief in a deified version of the Buddha.

↳ Est-ce que des esprits qui étaient auparavant humains sont présents:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Des êtres surnaturels non-humains sont présents:

– Yes

Notes: There are two miracle stories set in Mount Lu of this period (i.e. 350CE-450CE) that involve supernatural beings, although we do not know if these stories were known to the Mount Lu community members of this period, and if they were, how much significance they had. 1) When the Xunyang 潯陽 region (where Mount Lu is located) was being affected by draught, Huiyuan recited the _Hai longwang jing_ 海龍王經 (The Sūtra of the Dragon King of the Ocean) near a pond, upon which a snake (she 蛇) appeared from the pond and ascended to the sky. Soon after it started to rain, alleviating the draught. (T 2059.50:358a25-a28.) 2) Huiyuan's disciple Tanyong 曇邕 (d.u.) is reported to have imparted Buddhist precepts to a local mountain deity (shan shen 山神) and its twenty servants. (T 2059.50:362c26-363a2.)

↳ Ces êtres surnaturels peuvent être vus:

– Yes

↳ Ces êtres surnaturels peuvent être ressentis physiquement:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Les êtres surnaturels non-humains détiennent une connaissance de ce monde:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Des êtres surnaturels non-humains détiennent une efficacité causale délibérée dans le monde:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Des êtres surnaturels détiennent une efficacité causale indirecte dans le monde:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Ces êtres surnaturels manifestent des émotions positives:

– Yes

Notes: In the story involving Tanyong and the mountain deity discussed above, the deity expresses his wish to be ordained with Buddhist precepts.

↳ Ces êtres surnaturels manifestent des émotions négatives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Ces êtres surnaturels peuvent ressentir la faim:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Ces êtres surnaturels possèdent ou manifestent certaines autres caractéristiques [spécifiez]:

– Yes [specify]: The mountain deity in Tanyong's miracle story appears donning a formal garment (dan yi 單衣) and with twenty servants.

↳ Des êtres à la fois divins et humains sont présents:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

La surveillance surnaturelle est-elle présente:

"Surveillance surnaturelle" désigne la surveillance effectuée par des êtres surnaturels des comportements et/ou pensées des humains plus particulièrement en ce qui a trait aux normes sociales ou aux potentielles violations des norms.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Within the surviving literatures produced by and related to this group, there is no clear indication that supernatural monitoring was a meaningful element of the group's belief or practice. None of the miracle stories associated with the group seems to presuppose a mechanism of supernatural monitoring.

Est-ce que les êtres surnaturels infligent des punitions:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les êtres surnaturels confèrent des récompenses:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In the miracle story concerning Tanyong and the mountain deity, the deity rewards Tanyong with "utensils from a foreign region" (waiguo bijin 外國匕筋). But there aren't enough examples to decide if such a belief was a meaningful aspect of this group.

Messianism/Eschatology

Est-ce qu'il y a présence de croyances messianiques:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although the future Buddha Maitreya was an important Buddhist deity in some Buddhist communities in this period (e.g. Dao'an's community where Huiyuan started his monastic career), we

do not have any record of this cult being practiced by the members of the Mount Lu community.

Est-ce qu'il y a présence d'une eschatologie:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Y a-t-il des normes sociales générales prescrites par le groupe religieux:

– Yes

Notes: Like other Buddhist communities in early medieval China, the members of the Lu Shan community would have taken up the five precepts for lay Buddhists whose content bears on general social norms: 1) not killing, 2) not stealing, 3) no sexual misconduct, 4) no false speech, 5) no consumption of alcohol.

Y a-t-il une distinction entre conventions et morale au sein du groupe religieux:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert le célibat (abstinence sexuelle complète):

– No

Notes: The group consisted of both lay and monastic members.

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux pose des contraintes sur les relations sexuelles (abstinence sexuelle partielle):

– Yes

Notes: The monastics of the group would have been expected to maintain celibacy. The lay members, if we assume that they accepted the five lay precepts, would have been expected not to engage in adultery. Also, taking up the eight observances (ba guan 八關) on certain days of a month was an established practice in early Chinese Buddhism, one of the observances of which was abstinence from sex. But note that there is no record that members the Lu shan community carried out this practice.

Monogamie (hommes):

– Field doesn't know

Monogamie (femmes):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Autres contraintes sexuelles (hommes):

– Yes

Notes: The lay members, if we assume that they received the five lay precepts, would have been expected not to engage in adultery.

↳ Autres contraintes sexuelles (femmes):

– Yes

Notes: The lay members, if we assume that they received the five lay precepts, would have been expected not to engage in adultery. But note that there is no record of a female lay member of this community.

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert la castration:

– No

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert de faire des jeûnes:

– Yes

Notes: Although there is no record that the Mount Lu community also carried out this practice, taking up the eight observances (ba guan) on certain days of a month was a common Buddhist practice in early medieval China, one of the observances of which was to fast after noon.

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert la renonciation à des occasions de manger (tabous sur de la nourriture désirée):

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert des cicatrisations permanentes ou des altérations corporelles douloureuses:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert de mettre le corps dans des positions douloureuses ou le soumettre à des blessures douloureuses passagères:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert de sacrifier des adultes:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert de sacrifier des enfants:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular

Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert le sacrifice de soi (suicide):

– No

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert le sacrifice de ses biens personnels ou objets de valeur:

– No

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert un sacrifice de son temps (par exemple: pour assister à des réunions ou au service religieux, pour la prière régulières, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert de prendre des risques physiques:

– No

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert d'accepter des préceptes éthiques:

– Yes

Notes: The monastics would have been expected to be ordained with the full precepts (for more details about these precepts, see the note on "Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code?"), and the lay members would have been expected to be ordained with the five precepts. They would furthermore would likely have carried out the eight observances, although there is no record of this that survives.

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert d'être marginalisé par des membres à l'extérieur du groupe:

– No

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert de participer à des rituels à petite échelle (privé, dans le foyer familial):

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que l'appartenance à ce groupe religieux requiert de participer à des rituels à grande échelle:

[c'est-à-dire, impliquant la participation de deux foyers ou plus; cela inclut les "cérémonies" et les "festivals" à grande échelle]

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que des marqueurs extra-rituels sont présents au sein du groupe:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que le groupe emploie une terminologie fictive pour les liens de parenté:

– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

Quel est le meilleur qualificatif pour décrire la société à laquelle appartient le groupe religieux (s'il-vous-plaît, ne faites qu'un choix):

– An empire

Welfare

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question fournit de l'aide institutionnalisée en cas de famine:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que l'aide en cas de famine est disponible pour les membres du groupe à travers une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question fournit de l'aide institutionnalisée en cas de pauvreté:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que l'aide en cas de pauvreté est disponible pour les membres du groupe à travers une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question offre des soins institutionnalisés pour les personnes âgées et pour les personnes à mobilité réduite:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les soins institutionnalisés pour les personnes âgées et personnes à mobilité réduite sont disponibles pour les membres du groupe à travers une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Est-ce que le groupe religieux fournit une éducation formelle à ses membres:

– Yes

Notes: Although no detailed record about this group's educational practices survives, Buddhist monastic communities in medieval China are in general believed to have offered various types of education to its members. Many monks who studied on this mountain went on to become well-known scholar-monks of the time (e.g. Huiguan 慧觀 [375?-445?], Huirui 慧叡 [355-459], and Daosheng 道生 [355-434]). The Mount Lu community is also known for having offered an environment to lay intellectuals for focusing on their study while exchanging ideas with scholar-monks. For example, Lei Cizong 雷次宗 (386-448), who later became one of the teachers of the imperial crown prince of the Liu Song dynasty, is reported to have refined his expertise in Confucian ritual texts while studying on the mountain and learning from the lectures by Huiyuan (T 2059:50:361a22-27).

Est-ce que cette éducation formelle est réservée aux professionnels religieux:

– No

Est-ce que cette éducation est ouverte aux hommes comme aux femmes:

– Yes

Notes: The fact that a formal bhikṣuṇī saṃgha (community of Buddhist nuns) was very likely present on Mount Lu, receiving guidance from Huiyuan (T 2145.55:84a6-7), suggests that some form of education would have been available at least to female monastics.

Est-ce que cette éducation formelle est disponible pour les membres du groupe à travers une institution autre que le groupe religieux:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les membres du groupe interagissent avec d'autres bureaucraties institutionnelles:

– Yes

Notes: Although we do not know if it was an official function of the Mount Lu community, many individual members of the community maintained relationships with important government officials. See the note on "Does the religion have official political support?" above.

Public Works

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question fournit un espace public pour l'entreposage des aliments:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que l'entreposage public des aliments est fourni aux membres du groupe par une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question fournit un service de gestion des eaux (irrigation, contrôle des inondations):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There survives an anecdote in which the community's leader Huiyuan is reported to have started a rain by reciting the *_Hai longwang jing_ 海龍王經* when the region was affected by a drought; T 2059.50:358a25-28.

Est-ce que le service de gestion des eaux est fourni aux membres par une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question fournit une infrastructure de transport:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que l'infrastructure de transport est fournie aux membres par une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question prélève des taxes ou des dîmes:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les taxes sont prélevées aux membres par une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– No

Notes: It is generally believed that Buddhist monastic institutions were exempt from tax duties in early medieval China.

Enforcement

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question fournit une force policière institutionnalisée:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les membres du groupe interagissent avec une force policière fournie par une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question fournit des juges autorisés par l'institution:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les membres du groupe interagissent avec un système judiciaire fourni par une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question impose des punitions institutionnalisées:

– Yes

Notes: It is highly probably that the codes of conduct employed by this community (see below for details) detailed disciplinary measures against various transgressions.

Est-ce que les punitions institutionnelles incluent l'exécution:

– No

Est-ce que les punitions institutionnelles incluent l'exil:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les punitions institutionnelles incluent des peines corporelles:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les punitions institutionnelles incluent l'ostracisme:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les punitions institutionnelles incluent la saisie des biens:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les membres du groupe sont sujets à des punitions institutionnelles mises en oeuvre par une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question détient un code juridique formel:

– Yes

Notes: Huiyuan is known to have developed several sets of regulations governing his religious community (T 2126.54:241b8-9; T 2035.49:319a8). Although the details of these regulations do not survive, their titles do (T. 2145.55:84a3-6): *_Fashe jiedu_ 法社節度*, *_Waisi seng jiedu_ 外寺僧節度*, *_Jiedu_ 節度*, and *_Biqiuni jiedu_ 比丘尼節度*. It has been suggested that these four codes respectively dealt with the entirety of the Mount Lu community (consisting of lay and monastic members and visitors), the community of monks visiting from other monasteries, the community of resident monks, and lastly, the community of resident nuns.

Reference: Li 李, Xingling 幸玲. *Lushan Huiyuan Yanjiu 廬山慧遠研究*. Taipei: Wanjuanlou, 2007. p.282-83.

Reference: Li 李, Qinhe 勤合. *Lushan Huiyuan Jiaotuan Yanjiu 廬山慧遠教團研究*. Beijing: Shehui kexue wenxian chubanshe, 2016. p.p.152-53.

Reference: Tsukamoto, Zenryū, and Leon Hurvitz. *A History of Early Chinese Buddhism: From Its Introduction to the Death of Hui-yüan*. New York: Kodansha International, 1985. p.p.835-36.

Est-ce que les membres du groupe sont sujets à un code juridique formel fourni par une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question détient une force militaire institutionnalisée:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les membres du groupe participent à une force militaire institutionnalisée fournie par une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que les membres du groupe sont protégés ou soumis à une force militaire institutionnalisée fournie par une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Written Language

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question possède sa propre langue écrite:

– No

Est-ce que l'usage de cette langue distincte est réservé uniquement aux professionnels

religieux:

– Yes

Est-ce qu'une langue écrite, qui n'est pas particulièrement religieuse, est utilisée par les membres du groupe à travers une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Yes

Calendar

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question détient un calendrier formel:

– No

Est-ce que ce calendrier formel est fourni aux membres par une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Yes

Notes: They would have used the calendar set by the imperial court in Jiankang 建康.

Food Production

Est-ce que le groupe religieux en question fournit de la nourriture pour lui-même:

– Field doesn't know

Est-ce que la nourriture est fournie aux membres par une institution autre que le groupe religieux en question:

– Field doesn't know

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Wu 吳, Guofu 國富. *Lu Shan Daojiao Shi 廬山道教史*. Nanchang: Jiangxi renmin chubanshe, 2011.

Reference: Yes, Zürcher, Erik. *The Buddhist Conquest of China*. BRILL, 2007.
https://books.google.com/books/about/The_Buddhist_Conquest_of_China.html?hl=&id=GYsKhU7UW-cC. p.211-17., p.236-37.,

Reference: Yes, Tsukamoto, Zenryū, and Leon Hurvitz. *A History of Early Chinese Buddhism: From Its Introduction to the Death of Hui-yūan*. New York: Kodansha International, 1985. p.p.835-36.

Reference: Yes, Li 李, Xingling 幸玲. *Lushan Huiyuan Yanjiu 廬山慧遠研究*. Taipei: Wanjuanlou, 2007. p.282-83.

Reference: Yes, Li李, Qinhe勤合. Lushan Huiyuan Jiaotuan Yanjiu 庐山慧远教团研究. Beijing: Shehui kexue wenxian chubanshe, 2016. p.p.152-53.

Reference: Yes, Chen, Jinhua. "Buddhabhadra's (359-429) Collaboration with Huiyuan (334-416) in Transplanting the Nagarahāra Image-cave to China: A Reexamination". In Chūgoku Indo Shūkyōshi, Tokuni Bukkyō Shi Ni Okeru Shomotsu No Ryūtsū Denpa to Jinbutsu Idō No Chiiki Tokusei 中国印度宗教史とくに仏教史における書物の流通伝播と人物移動の地域特性, edited by Tōru徹 Funayama船山. Kyoto: Kyōto Daigaku Jinbun Kagaku Kenkyūjo, 2011.

Reference: Yes, Jones, Charles B.. "Was Lushan Huiyuan a Pure Land Buddhist? Evidence from His Correspondence with Kumārajīva About Nianfo Practice". Zhonghua Foxue Xuebao 21 (January 1, 2008).

Reference: Yes, Park, Jungnok. How Buddhism Acquired a Soul on the Way to China. Equinox, n.d..